

Child Pornography

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Introduction

Pornography is a serious issue that will never be ignored or dismissed - focusing directly with child pornography. Pornography, viewed by an adult is a pill stimulating the mind, inducing sexual arousal and pleasure, but when a child views pornography, an affect of social behaviour starts. This child not only represents him or herself in the world, but also represents the worlds youth altogether. Often pornography is the first exposure children have to sexually explicit subject matter, so it can set the standard for normal or appropriate sexual behaviour. Teenage boys are the biggest consumers of pornography. Teenagers dont just look they learn from pornography. The use of sexual media is clearly associated with sexually aggressive behaviour. Some believe that it can cause addiction or compulsive sexual behaviour, and almost all believe that it facilitates, maintains or reinforces it. This is particularly true if the pornography is arousing, if it is coupled with masturbation and subsequent orgasm.

Children today are growing up whose earliest sexual imprinting derives not from a living human being but from fantasies of their own. From the lack of knowledge and maturity, children use pornography literature and illustrations to teach them how sexuality really is. It is hard for a child to come forth and search the answers from their parents.

When a child’s interest in aimed toward sex education, the easiest solution to learning is to seek a source that will inform the most and with the lease moral resistance. Twenty-nine per cent of boys rated pornography over parents, teachers, and books, school and peers as their source for the most useful information about sex

Children and Online Pornography

The volume and easy availability of online pornography have given rise to recurrent public concerns and occasional moral panics especially related to child pornography and children’s access to materials deemed adult (e.g., Patterson, 2004: pp. 104–105). As early as in 1995, the Times ‘cyberporn’ issue liberally categorized over 80% of all photographs online as pornographic. Since only an estimated 16 million people used the Internet globally at that point, the issue, with its inflated and unsubstantiated estimates, was

effective in shaping the national imagination concerning the new medium and its contents in the United States (Chun, 2006: pp. 77–80). Due to prosecution, child pornography has nevertheless not been a visible feature on the Web and P2P networks for file sharing among users have been heavily regulated (Greenfield, 2004; Coopersmith, 2006: pp. 14–15). Child pornography is mainly distributed in closed networks and in the so-called deep web that is inaccessible to search engines and therefore excluded from mass consumption.

Child protection remains a central strand in debates on online pornography, often in connection with acts of regulation. In the summer of 2013, Prime Minister David Cameron’s government in the United Kingdom announced that, in the name of child protection, all Internet service providers in the country are to block access to online porn unless the customer specifically sets the filters off. In Australia, online content is classified for similar ends. In countries where such centralized filtering is not in place, local regulation can be bypassed by hosting the illegal content on a server located in another country.

Kinds of Child Pornography

Here are some examples of the different kinds of child pornography

- visual representation (that is, a photo, film, video or another image) of a minor taking part in a clearly sexual activity
- visual representation of certain parts of a minor’s body for a sexual purpose
- encouraging, showing (for example in a photo, film, video or another image) or describing a sexual activity with a minor that is forbidden

Child pornography can be in different forms, for example, in pictures, videos, written material or sound recordings.

Effects of Child Pornography

The vast majority of children who appear in child pornography have not been abducted or physically forced to participate. [32] In most cases they know the producers may even be their father and are manipulated into taking part by more subtle means. Nevertheless, to be the subject of child pornography can have devastating physical, social, and psychological effects on children. [33].

The children portrayed in child pornography are first victimized when their abuse is perpetrated and recorded. They are further victimized each time that record is accessed. In one study, [34] 100 victims of child pornography were interviewed about the effects of their exploitation at the time it occurred and in later years. Referring to when the abuse was taking place, victims described the physical pain (e.g., around the genitals), accompanying somatic symptoms (such as headaches, loss of appetite, and sleeplessness), and feelings of psychological distress (emotional isolation, anxiety, and fear). However, most also felt a pressure to cooperate with the offender and not to disclose the offence, both out of loyalty to the offender and a sense of shame about their own behaviour. Only five cases were ultimately reported to authorities. In later years, the victims reported that initial feelings of shame and anxiety did not fade but intensified to feelings of deep despair, worthlessness, and hopelessness. Their experience had provided them with a distorted model of sexuality, and many had particular difficulties in establishing and maintaining healthy emotional and sexual relationships.

Effects on Users

The effects of pornography on users have been extensively researched but results are contentious. There are at least five possible relationships between pornography use and the sexual abuse of children:

- Pornography use is an expression of existing sexual interests. An individual who sexually abuses children seeks out child pornography as part of his/her pattern of sexual gratification. [35] The offender’s sexual interests cause his/her pornography use rather than the other way around.
- Pornography is used to prime the individual to offend. An individual deliberately views child pornography immediately before offending. Pornography is used in the short term to sexually stimulate the offender in preparation for offending.[36]
- Pornography has a corrosive effect. An individual becomes increasingly interested in child pornography, is attracted to images of increasing severity, and becomes desensitized to the harm victims experience. Use of pornography in the long term may also increase the risk that the person will sexually abuse a child.[37]
- Pornography has a cathartic effect. Viewing child pornography is the sole outlet for an individual’s sexual attraction to children. Pornography use may substitute for, or even help the individual resist, engaging in hands-on offending.[38]
- Pornography is a by-product of paedophilia. Pornography is created in the process of carrying out sexual abuse or is used to groom potential victims and prepare them for abuse. [39] Pornography is incidental to the abuse suffered by the victim.

In all likelihood, the effects of child pornography vary among users, and all of the above relationships may apply depending upon the individual in question.

Possible Crimes that Deal with Child Pornography

The Criminal Code forbids activities that deal with child pornography. For example, it is forbidden to do these things:

- make child pornography
- print child pornography
- publish child pornography
- distribute child pornography
- transmit (send) child pornography
- make child pornography available
- sell child pornography
- import child pornography
- export child pornography
- possess (have) child pornography
- access (look up or get hold of) child pornography
- advertise child pornography

The law says that Internet service providers have to tell the police as soon as possible if they think someone is using their services for child pornography, for example, through Internet connections, hosting services (using Internet servers) or email. Internet service providers are the companies that sell you your internet service.

Child Pornography in India

Child pornography is a crime in India. Information Technology Act, 2000 & Indian Penal Code, 1860 protects child pornography. Child is the person who is below the age of 18 years.[12]

In February 2009, the Parliament of India passed the Information Technology Bill which made creation and transmission of child pornography illegal. The newly passed Information Technology Bill is set to make it illegal to not only create and transmit child pornography in any electronic form, but even to browse it. The punishment for a first offence of publishing, creating, exchanging,

downloading or browsing any electronic depiction of children in “obscene or indecent or sexually explicit manner” can attract five years in jail and a fine of Rs 10 lakh.[13]

Section 67 of the existing act deals with “publishing obscene information in electronic form”. It is a generally worded section that does not specifically define “pornography” or make it an offence, and does not mention “child pornography” at all. But in its amended avatar, Section 67B proposes specifically to punish involvement in sexually explicit online or electronic content that depicts children. It will also be an offence to “cultivate, entice or induce children to online relationship with other children for a sexual act.”[14].

Punishment for first conviction with imprisonment which may extend to 3 years & fine which may extend to 5 lakhs rupees. And for subsequent offence imprisonment which may extend to 5 years & fine which may extend to 10 lakhs rupees. Section 292 of the Indian Penal Code, 1860 does not per se deal with obscenity online.[15].

Conclusion

Developing a precise definition for the term ‘obscenity’ is difficult. What may be considered as obscene in one country may not be considered as obscene in another. It mainly depends on the moral and ethical values of the people who belong to a specific country. However, the generic definition of obscenity refers to an act or speech or item that is likely to corrupt the morality of the general public because of its indecency or lewdness in content or form. The exhibition of something offensive to modesty or decency or expression of unchaste or lustful ideas or being indecent or lewd is considered to be obscene, in most countries. In my opinion to control child pornography in India we should completely ban porn sites. This stringent action can solve the problem to a larger extent. This would give us time to think and plan some new ways to eradicate child pornography from India. Depiction of minors, both real and virtual, as well as adults appearing to be minors, in electronic child pornography should be prevented by Indian law. Stringent measures must be taken to combat such heinous abuse.

Web Sources

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